

Synthesis and some Reactions of β -Ketoanilides

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2,6-Diarylidencyclohexanones react with acetoacetanilides in a Michael condensation to give the corresponding β -ketoanilides. The synthesis of a series of compounds is described. Their structures were confirmed by analytical, ir and nmr spectral data.

β -KETOANILIDES are versatile reagents and have been extensively utilised in synthesis. Treatment of **1a-c**^{1,4} with acetoacetanilides in the presence of sodium methoxide gave the corresponding β -ketoanilide derivatives (**2a-i**) as inferred from their elemental analysis and ir spectra which showed defined bands characteristic for NH, C=O, and CONH groups, and ¹H nmr (deuteriochloroform) spectral peaks at δ 7.7-7.0 (1H, m, Ar), 7.3 (1H, s, NH) and 6.9 (1H, s, =CH).

1a; Ar=C₆H₅
1b; Ar=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p
1c; Ar=C₆H₄-CH₃-p

2a; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₅
2b; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p
2c; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p
2d; Ar=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p, Ar'=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p
2e; Ar=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p, Ar'=C₆H₅
2f; Ar=C₆H₅-OCH₃-p, Ar'=C₆H₅-OCH₃-p
2g; Ar=C₆H₄-CH₃-p, Ar'=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p
2h; Ar=C₆H₄-CH₃-p, Ar'=C₆H₅
2i; Ar=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p, Ar'=C₆H₄-CH₃

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1*

Compd. no.	Colour	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
1a	Yellow	115	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O
1b	Yellow	160	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O
1c	Pale yellow	171	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O

*Compounds obtained in good yields and gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2

Compd. no.	Colour	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
					C	H
2a	Yellow	190	49	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₂	82.91 (83.14)	6.37 (6.23)
2b	Yellow	207	56	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ NO ₂	83.12 (83.22)	6.18 (6.49)
2c	Brown	183	50	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ NO ₂	80.01 (80.35)	6.36 (6.26)
2d	Yellow	145	45	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₂	77.96 (78.11)	6.39 (6.51)
2e	Brown	110	55	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₂	77.48 (77.89)	6.18 (6.29)
2f	Brown	130	40	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₂	75.29 (75.72)	6.13 (6.31)
2g	White	197	40	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₂	80.19 (80.65)	6.47 (6.72)
2h	Yellow	150	52	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₂	83.10 (83.30)	6.81 (6.73)
2i	Brown	158	47	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₂	83.12 (83.40)	6.91 (6.94)

Reaction of **2a-i** with hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine, and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine in acetic acid containing freshly fused sodium acetate afforded the corresponding pyrazolone derivatives (**3a-e**)². These compounds were characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectral data (Table 3).

3a; Ar=C₆H₅, R=H
3b; Ar=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p, R=H
3c; Ar=C₆H₄-CH₃-p, R=H
3d; Ar=C₆H₅, R=C₆H₅
3e; Ar=C₆H₅, R=C₆H₄-NO₂-p

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It seems that the reaction involved in the first stage the hydrazone formation and then cyclisation to the pyrazolone derivative of type 3 under the influence of acetic acid and sodium acetate. In order to verify such mechanism, when **2a** was

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Compd. no.	Colour	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				O	H
3a ^a	White	288	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O	80.98 (81.35)	5.97 (6.21)
3b ^a	White	275	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	75.12 (75.36)	6.12 (6.28)
3c ^a	White	283	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O	81.15 (81.67)	6.49 (6.80)
3d ^b	Green	140	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	83.89 (83.72)	6.15 (6.64)
3e ^b	Green	185	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	75.39 (75.78)	5.17 (5.26)

^a $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 700 (C=O) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N).
^b $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) disappearance of (NH) band, 1 700 (C=O) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

treated with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol, the corresponding hydrazone (4) was obtained. The structure was confirmed by correct analytical figures and infrared spectrum which showed absorption bands at 3 300 (NH) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (CONH). The treatment of 4 with acetic acid and sodium acetate gave a product which could be formulated as 3a on the basis of its analysis and infrared spectrum.

Treatment of 2a-d with different aromatic diazonium salts gave the corresponding arylazo derivatives (5a-1). These compounds were characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectral data (Table 4).

- 5a; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₅, Ar''=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p
 5b; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₅, Ar''=C₆H₄-NO₂-p
 5c; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₅, Ar''=C₆H₄-OH₃-p
 5d; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₅, Ar''=C₆H₄-Cl-m
 5e; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₄-OH₃-p, Ar''=C₆H₄-OOH₃-p
 5f; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₄-OH₃-p, Ar''=C₆H₄-NO₂-p
 5g; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₄-OH₃-p, Ar''=C₆H₄-OH₃-p
 5h; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p, Ar''=C₆H₄-OOH₃-p
 5i; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p, Ar''=C₆H₄-OH₃-p
 5j; Ar=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p, Ar'=C₆H₄-OH₃-p, Ar''=C₆H₄-OOH₃-p
 5k; Ar=C₆H₄-OCH₃-p, Ar'=C₆H₄-OH₃-p, Ar''=C₆H₄-OH₃-p
 5l; Ar=C₆H₄-OOH₃-p, Ar'=C₆H₄-OH₃-p, Ar''=C₆H₄-NO₂-p

Treatment of 2a with benzalacetone in butanol and piperidine gave the Michael adduct (6) as inferred from its elemental analysis and ir spectral data, $\nu_{\max}$ 1 740 (CO) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (CONH).

Treatment of 2a with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in acetic acid solution led to the formation of the oxazolone derivative (7). It seems that the reaction involves in its first stage the formation of the oxime compound (8) which cyclises to the

 TABLE 4—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5^a

Compd. no.	Colour	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				O	H
5a	Brown	170	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	78.15 (78.30)	5.47 (5.80)
5b	Reddish brown	179	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	73.87 (74.23)	5.01 (5.15)
5c	Brown	171	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	80.15 (80.58)	5.72 (5.90)
5d	Deep red	138	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	75.67 (75.52)	5.41 (5.24)
5e	Deep brown	144	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	78.32 (78.48)	6.17 (6.02)
5f	Orange	158	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	74.24 (74.49)	5.51 (5.37)
5g	Red	152	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	80.37 (80.70)	6.01 (6.19)
5h	Brown	148	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	76.72 (76.38)	5.71 (5.86)
5i	Brown	163	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	78.71 (78.48)	6.12 (6.02)
5j	Red	155	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	74.35 (74.88)	6.27 (6.08)
5k	Brown	130	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	76.39 (76.80)	6.19 (6.24)
5l	Reddish brown	150	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	70.97 (71.34)	5.17 (5.48)

^a $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 715 (CO), 1 650 (CONH) and 1 520 cm^{-1} (N=N).

Scheme 1

corresponding oxazolone (7) under the influence of acetic acid. In order to verify such mechanism, the oxime (8) was prepared by the interaction of

2a with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanol. When the oxime was refluxed in acetic acid, a rapid change of colour was immediately observed and **8** was obtained. The identity of the oxazolone (**7**) obtained with the reaction in acetic acid with that obtained by cyclisation of **8** was established by analytical, m.m.p. and ir spectral data.

Reaction of **2a** with *o*-phenylenediamine in hot acetic acid gave the benzonaphthadiazepinone derivative (**9**). On the other hand, condensation of **2a** with *o*-phenylenediamine in ethanol led to the formation of anilide (**10**), which was confirmed by cyclisation under the influence of acetic acid and sodium acetate to **9**. The formation of **9** and **10** is believed to proceed as shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

The identity of **9** obtained by direct interaction of **2a** with *o*-phenylenediamine in acetic acid solution with that obtained by cyclisation of **10** was established by the analytical, m.m.p. and ir spectral data.

Fusion of **2a** with diethyl malonate in the presence of sodium acetate gave **11** as inferred from its elemental analysis and ir spectrum which showed bands characteristic for NH and ester groups.

Since the condensation of urea or thiourea with diethyl malonate or its mono- or di-substituted derivatives provides a route to pyrimidines or substituted-pyrimidines⁸, the condensation of **9** with thiourea in the presence of sodium methoxide affords the thiobarbituric acid derivative (**12**). The structure of this compound was confirmed by its analytical data and ir spectrum which displayed bands characteristic for NH, CO and C=S groups and the absence of the ester stretching.

Experimental

Elemental analyses were performed in the Micro-analytical Unit, Faculty of Science, Mansoura University. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Pye- Unicam SP-1200 spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra were obtained at 60 MHz, using TMS as an internal standard. Melting points are uncorrected.

2,6-Diarylidene-3,4,5-trihydro-1-(2H-cyclohexanone): To a stirred mixture of cyclohexanone (0.01 mol) and the aromatic aldehydes (0.02 mol) was added slowly 4% ethanolic potassium hydroxide (20 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for further 2 h and left overnight. The resulting precipitated solid was washed with ethanol, water and crystallised from ethanol to give compounds **1a-c**, which gave satisfactory elemental analyses (Table 1).

Reaction of 2,6-diarylidene-1-cyclohexanone with acetoacetanilides. Formation of 2a-i: To **1a-c** (0.01 mol) in potassium methoxide (0.02 mol), the appropriate acetoacetanilide (0.01 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then poured onto ice-cold dilute HCl, and the resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from proper solvent to give compounds **2a-i** (Table 2); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 030 (NH), 1 710 (CO) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (CONH).

Reaction of 2a-i with hydrazines in acetic acid. Formation of 3a-e: A mixture of **2a-c** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine, phenylhydrazine and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The separated solid on cooling was filtered and crystallised from the appropriate solvent to give compounds **3a-e** (Table 3).

Reaction of 2a with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol. Formation of 4: A mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solid that separated on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give **4** as white crystals (70%), m.p. 270° (Found: C, 80.15; H, 6.19. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires: C, 80.53; H, 6.48%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300 (NH), 1 650 (CONH) and 1 635 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Conversion of 4 into 3a: A mixture of **4**, acetic acid and sodium acetate was fused together for 2 h at 280°. The solid product was proved to be **3a** by its m.p., m.m.p. and ir spectral data.

Reaction of 2a-d with aryldiazonium salts. Formation of 5a-1: To a cold solution of **2a-d** (0.01 mol) in each case in ethanol containing potassium hydroxide, the appropriate diazonium salt (0.01 mol) was added dropwise with stirring and then acidified with dilute acetic acid. The resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give **5a** (Table 4).

Reaction of 2a with benzalacetone. Formation of 6: Benzalacetone (0.01 mol) was added to **2a** (0.01 mol) in butanol (30 ml) containing a few drops of piperidine. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then poured onto excess water, and the resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give the product as brown crystals (**6**; 60%, m.p. 139° (Found: C, 84.97; H, 6.07. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}$ requires: C, 85.56; H, 6.23%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 740 (CO) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (CONH).

Reaction of 2a with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in acetic acid. Formation of 7: A mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01

mol) in acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was poured onto cold water, and the resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give the product as brown crystals (**7**; 65%), m.p. 172° (Found: C, 81.37; H, 5.82. $C_{24}H_{21}NO_2$ requires: C, 81.12; H, 5.91%); ν_{max} 1 680 (CO) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Reaction of 2a with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanol. **Formation of 8:** An ethanolic mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (1 g) was refluxed for 4 h. The resulting solid on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give the product as white crystals (**8**; 60%), m.p. 222° (Found: C, 80.12; H, 6.49. $C_{30}H_{28}N_2O_2$ requires: C, 80.35; H, 6.25%); ν_{max} 3 400 (OH of oxime) and 3 030 cm^{-1} (NH).

Conversion of 8 into 7: A mixture of **8** and acetic acid was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid was proved to be **7** by its m.p., m.m.p. and ir spectral data.

Reaction of 2a with o-phenylenediamine in acetic acid. **Formation of 9:** A mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol) and o-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (40 ml) was refluxed for 20 min and filtered while hot. The resulting solid on standing was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid to give the product as brown crystals (**9**; 70%), m.p. 160° (Found: C, 83.54; H, 6.16. $C_{30}H_{26}N_2O$ requires: C, 83.72; H, 6.05%); ν_{max} 3 300 (NH), 1 700 (CO) and 1 615 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 10.2 (cyclic CONH).

Reaction of 2a with o-phenylenediamine in ethanol. **Formation of 10:** An ethanolic mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol) and o-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol) was refluxed

for 4 h. The resulting solid separated on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give the product as brown crystals (**10**; 70%), m.p. 195° (Found: C, 82.37; H, 6.53. $C_{36}H_{33}N_2O$ requires: C, 82.60; H, 6.31%).

Conversion of 10 into 9: A solution of **10** in acetic acid was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid was proved to be **9** by its m.p., m.m.p. and ir spectral data.

Reaction of 2a with diethyl malonate. **Formation of 11:** A mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol), diethyl malonate (0.01 mol) and freshly fused sodium acetate (1 g) was fused together at 170° for 2 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give the product as pale brown crystals (**11**, 63%), m.p. 130° (Found: C, 77.78; H, 6.52. $C_{27}H_{27}NO_5$ requires: C, 77.21; H, 6.43%); ν_{max} 1 740 cm^{-1} (ester).

Reaction of 11 with thiourea. **Formation of 12:** A solution of **11** in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was treated with thiourea (0.12 mol) and refluxed for 10 h with sodium methoxide (3%). The mixture was kept overnight and then acidified with acetic acid. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give the product as brown crystals (**12**; 60%), m.p. 185° (Found: C, 73.31; H, 5.32. $C_{34}H_{29}N_3O_3S$ requires: C, 72.99; H, 5.19%); ν_{max} 3 410 (NH), 1 675 (CO) and 1 160 cm^{-1} (C=S).

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